

Synthesis and Chemistry of some Novel 3-Heteroaryl-quinazolin-4-one Derivatives and their Antimicrobial Effects

S. G. ABDEL-HAMIDE

Pharmaceutical Chemistry Department, Faculty of Pharmacy, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 6 March 1995, revised 18 March 1996, accepted 24 July 1996

Some new heteroaryl-quinazolin-4-ones have been synthesised via the interaction of 3-amino-2-phenyl-6-iodoquinazolin-4-one with some oxo-compounds. Significant *in vitro* antimicrobial activities have been observed for some members of the series.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ on the synthesis of various heterocyclic systems derived from 3-amino-quinazolin-4-one moiety, some more 3-heteroaryl-quinazolin-4-one systems have been synthesised from reaction of compound 2 with some oxo-compounds followed by cyclisation reactions. Their antimicrobial activity has been studied.

Results and Discussion

Reaction of 3-amino-2-phenyl-6-iodoquinazolin-4-one (2)¹ with aromatic aldehydes in refluxing ethanol/piperidine/dioxane and/or acetic acid yielded 3-arylidine derivatives (3a-i). Subjecting compounds 3 to the action of HCN

in glacial acetic acid/ethanol, *p*-chlorothiophenol (by fusion) and/or mercaptoacetic acid (in dry benzene) afforded 4-6 respectively. These addition reactions may proceed via addition across exocyclic C=N^{4,5} followed by cyclisation (6) (Scheme 1).

In a program to obtain potent antimicrobial agents, it was considered of interest to synthesise a series of 3-heteroaryl-quinazolin-4-one derivatives and related compounds. Thus, compound 2 was allowed to react with different oxo-cyclic compounds, such as aryl anhydride and/or oxazolin-5-ones to yield phthalamido derivatives (7a-g) and/or imidazolones (8a-b) respectively. Mass fragmentation pattern is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

On the other hand, compound 1 was refluxed with different sulphadiazines in dry pyridine³ to give 2,3,6-trisubstituted-quinazolin-4-ones (9a-c).

Acylation of compound 2 with acetyl chloride in DMF led to the formation of *N*-acetyl derivative (10) which on fusion with the hydrazine hydrate afforded 2-phenyl-5-methyl-10-iodo-4*H*-quinazolino[3,4-*b*][1,2,4,5]tetrazine (11), while compound 10 on refluxing with ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid gave benzoxazinone 1 (Scheme 3). The isolated benzoxazinone (1) from reaction of 10 with glacial acetic acid is due to nucleophilic attack of cyclic C=O and C=N in quinazolinone moiety.

Trials to formylate compound 2 using DMF-POCl₃ adduct (Vilsmeier-Haak reagent)⁴ gave the *N*-formyl 13 which upon acylation by refluxing in acetic anhydride or treatment with acetyl chloride in DMF afforded benzoxazinone

(1). Condensation of 13 with ethanolamine in absolute ethanol afforded the arylidene (14) which on stirring with concentrated H₂SO₄ gave 4,5-tetrahydro-1-(2-phenyl-7-iodoquinazolin-4-one-3-yl)imidazole (15). In addition, condensation of 13 with hydrazine hydrate yielded the hydrazone (16) which on reaction with glacial acetic acid-fused sodium acetate gave 2-phenyl-10-iodo-4*H*-quinazolino[3,4-*b*][1,2,4,5]tetrazine (17) (Scheme 3). Mass spectrum of 17 exhibited a molecular ion peak at m/z 387 (abnd. 0.7%) which further underwent fragmentation processes supporting its structure (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. Mass fragmentation pattern of compound 17

The nucleophilic attack between diethyl oxalate and 16 in sodium ethylate yielded the amino 18 which upon refluxing in acetic anhydride gave benzoxazinone (1).

Our approach to the synthesis of 3-heteroaryl-quinazolin-4-ones by refluxing of 16 with *p*-bromophenyl bromide in ethanol⁵ and/or fusion with benzoic acid hydrazide⁶ gave 5,6-tetrahydro-6-aryl-4-(2-phenyl-7-iodoquinazolin-4-one-3-yl)-1,2,4-triazine (19) and/or 3-(3'-

Scheme 3

phenyl-5-triazol-4-yl)-2-phenyl-7-iodoquinazolin-4-one (20) respectively.

Antimicrobial activity : The compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activities by the standard method⁷ at concentration level 3 mg ml⁻¹ in DMF and the results are given in Table 1. Almost all the compounds showed promising antimicrobial activity. The presence of imidazolone (8a), thioether (5b) and imidazole (15) moieties augments the antimicrobial activity remarkably. The compounds with S-atom are more active than those with alkyl and/or aryl moiety. Finally, all the 3-heteroaryl-quinazolin-4-ones are in general about two times more active than the Schiff bases 3a,b. The growth inhibiting activity of the compounds towards *E. coli*, *B. subt.*, *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* was evaluated for comparison and they show equal potency against all tested strains of bacteria when compared with gentamycin.

TABLE 1—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY DATA (INHIBITION ZONES, mm) OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	<i>E.c</i>	<i>B.s</i>	<i>C.a</i>	<i>S.a</i>
3a	—	—	8	11
3b	—	10	9	8
3c	13	—	10	1
3d	—	9	8	6
5a	13	11	12	13
5b	15	17	12	14
6a	14	12	13	11
6b	12	10	10	8
7a	—	8	6	13
7b	13	10	—	12
7c	6	—	5	—
7e	—	6	8	11
7g	—	8	10	12
8a	20	14	15	16
8b	16	12	—	12
9a	—	10	7	10
9b	11	13	—	8
9c	13	—	9	12
15	15	13	16	19
17	16	14	15	15
19	14	15	12	11
Gentamycin	31	25	21	29

E.c = *E. coli*, *B.s* = *B. subtilis*, *C.a* = *C. albicans*, *S.a* = *S. aureus*

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMS) on a EM 390 NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a GCMS qp 1000 ex Schimadzu

instrument (70 eV). Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer CHN 240A analyser and all compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using CCl₄-ethyl acetate (10 : 1) as mobile phase. Column chromatography was carried out on Merck 60 silica gel (70–230 mesh). Compounds 1, 2 and 12 were prepared by the reported method¹.

Synthesis of Schiff bases (3a-1) : An equimolar mixture of 3-amino-2-phenyl-7-iodoquinazolin-4-one (2) and the appropriate aldehydes in proper solvent was refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from proper solvent to give the products (39–60%) : 3a, m.p. 229° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 080 (Ar-CH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N), 1 510, 1 480 (aliph. CH), 900, 840 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph), λ_{\max} 281, 244 and 229 nm; b, 225° (AcOH); c, 225° (AcOH); d, 207° (AcOH); e, 213° (AcOH); f, 208° (AcOH); g, 156° (AcOH); h, 228° (AcOH); i, 212° (AcOH); j, 209° (AcOH); l, 230° (AcOH); k, 157° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 020 (Ar-CH), 2 950 (aliph. CH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 640 (C=C-C=C), 1 590 (C=N), 1 490 (aliph. CH) and 900, 580 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph), λ_{\max} 303, 267, 250 and 228 nm, δ 2.0 (3H, CH₃), 3.5 (1H, CH-N), 6.5–7.2 (2H, -CH=CH-) and 7.7–8.0, 8.2–8.8 (m, ArH).

Addition reactions on compounds 3 : (i) **Addition of HCN (Formation of cyano derivative 4) :** A mixture of 3h (0.01 mol) and KCN (0.01 mol in 10 ml H₂O) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and diluted with cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised to give 4 (50%), m.p. 335° (DMF), ν_{\max} 3 165 (NH), 3 049 (Ar-CH), 2 234 (C=N), 1 755 (C=O), 1 596 (C=N), 1 461 (aliph. CH) and 902, 861 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph). (ii) **Addition of thiol on compounds 3b,d (Formation of 4a,b) :** A mixture of 3b and 3d (0.01 mol) and *p*-chlorothiophenol was fused at 200° for 1 h, then cooled and the solid thus obtained was crystallised to give 5a and/or 5b : 5a (60%), m.p. 283° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 200 (NH), 2 900 (aliph. CH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N), 1 480 (aliph. CH), 1 310 (NCSN), 1 050 (C-S) and 970, 830 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph); 5b (40%), m.p. 241° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 200 (NH), 2 950 (aliph. CH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 490 (aliph. CH), 1 170 (C-S), 830 (aryl...Ph) and 700 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). (iii) **Cycloaddition of mercaptoacetic acid on compounds 3a-g (Synthesis of thiazolidin-4-one 6a and 6b) :** A mixture of 3a and 3g (0.01 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.02 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml), and anhydrous sodium sulphate (5 g) was refluxed for 48 h, then filtered hot and concentrated by evaporation to one-third of its volume. The resulting solid was crystallised to give 6a and/or 6b : 6a (46%), m.p. 184° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 550–3 450 (OH), 2 910 (aliph. CH), 1 750–1 700 (C=O), 1 630–1 590 (C=N), 1 470 cm⁻¹ (aliph. CH), λ_{\max} 295, 254 and 228 nm, δ 3.5

(2H, CH₂), 4.2 (1H, CH=), 6.1 (1H, CH), 7.2–7.5, 7.6–7.9 (m, ArH) and 9.0 (1H, Ph–OH); **6b** (30%), m.p. 334° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 550–2 450 (OH), 2 950 (aliph. CH) and 1 870–1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O), *m/z* (abundance %), 540 (0.37%), 348 (100%) and 334.5 (2.46%).

N-Substituted-phthalimido derivatives (7a-g): An equimolar mixture of compound **2** and the appropriate anhydride in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) with sodium acetate (0.5 g) was refluxed for 18 h, and then concentrated by evaporation. The solid so obtained was dried and crystallised to give **7a-g** (50–30%): **7a**, m.p. 191° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 1 820, 1 780, 1 730 (C=O), 1 630–1 610 (C=N), 1 240 (N–N) and 920, 880, 850 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph); **b**, 185° (AcOH); **c**, 236° (AcOH); **d**, 287° (AcOH); **e**, 231° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 1 830, 1 780, 1 730 (C=O), 1 630, 1 610 (C=N), 1 250 (N–N), 920, 870 (aryl...Ph) and 710 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl), δ 2.3 (2H, CH₂), 3.5 (1H, CH), 5.7 (2H, –CH=CH–), 7.6–8.0, 8.3–8.5 (m, ArH), **f**, 238° (AcOH); **g**, 205° (AcOH).

Imidazolone derivatives (8a,b): An equimolar mixture of compound **2** and the appropriate oxazolone derivatives in dry pyridine (50 ml) was refluxed for 10 h, then cooled and acidified with dilute HCl. The formed solid was crystallised (40–30%); **8a**, m.p. 120° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 1 770 (C=O), 1 680 (C=O), 1 620 (C=C), 1 250 (N–N), 920, 840 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph); **b**, *m/z* 668.

3-(p-Sulphonamidophenyl)-2-phenyl-6-iodoquinazolin-4-ones (9a-c): A mixture of compound **1** (0.01 mol) and/or the appropriate sulpha drugs (0.02 mol) in dry pyridine (50 ml) was refluxed for 18 h, then cooled and neutralised with dilute HCl. The solid so obtained was crystallised (40–35%); **9a**, m.p. 285° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 320 (NH), 3 050 (aryl CH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 330 (SO₂), 1 150 (C–S) and 950, 870 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph); **b**, m.p. 275° (AcOH); **c**, 290° (AcOH).

N-Acyl derivative (10): A mixture of compound **2** (0.01 mol) and acetyl chloride (0.01 mol) in DMF (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 4 h, then cooled and poured onto ice. The resulting solid was crystallised (40%): m.p. 210° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 163 (NH), 3 041 (aryl CH), 1 755 (C=O), 1 672 (C=O), 1 595 (C=N), 1 475 (aliph. CH) and 905, 860 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph).

Quinazolinotetrazine (11): A mixture of **10** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was fused under reflux for 1 h, then cooled and triturated with methanol to give **11** (20%), m.p. 330° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 610 (NH), 3 060 (aryl CH), 2 980 (aliph. CH), 1 590 (C=N), 1 470 (aliph. CH) and 920, 840 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph).

Amination of 10 (Isolation of 1 and 12): A mixture of **10** (0.01 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled and poured onto ice. The aqueous layer was extracted with chloroform (30 ml) and the extract was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and concentrated. The residue was

622

purified by column chromatography with hexane and increasing amount of ethyl acetate to give 6-iodo-2-aryl-4*H*-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (**1**) and 2-benzoylamino-5-iodoanthranilic acid (**12**) respectively.

N-Formyl derivative (13): A mixture of **2** (0.01 mol), DMF (15 ml) and POCl₃ (8 ml) was stirred for 2 h and the resulting solid was crystallised (60%), m.p. 250° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 300–2 700 (NH, CHO), 1 700, 1 600 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 250–1 200 (N–N) and 910, 870 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph).

Condensation of 13 with ethanolamine (Formation of imino 14): A mixture of **13** (0.005 mol) and ethanolamine (0.05 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled. The isolated solid was crystallised (40%), m.p. 120° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 400 (OH), 3 300–3 250 (NH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 450 (aliph. CH) and 820 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph).

Imidazole derivative (15): A suspension of **14** (0.4 g) in conc. H₂SO₄ (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and then neutralised with aqueous NaOH, diluted with cold water and filtered. The residue was crystallised (30%), m.p. 160° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 060 (aryl CH), 2 920 (aliph. CH), 1 675 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N), 1 440 (aliph. CH) and 910, 870 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph), δ 3.4–3.7 (4H, m, CH₂–CH₂), 5.9 (1H, CH=N), 7.8–8.0, 8.2–8.5 (m, ArH).

Condensation of 13 with hydrazine hydrate: A mixture of **13** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.03 mol) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 30 min, then cooled. The solid thus obtained was crystallised to give **16** (50%), m.p. 150° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH₂), 3 200 (NH), 3 050 (aryl CH), 2 950 (aliph. CH), 1 670 (C=O) and 1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Cyclisation of 16 (Formation of heterobicyclic 17): Compound **16** (1 g) was heated above its m.p. (>50°) for 1 h, then cooled and titrated with methanol to give **17** (40%), m.p. 329° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 100 (NH), 3 050 (aryl CH), 1 650 (C=N), 1 590 (C=N) and 930, 820 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph), *m/z* 387 (0.7%).

Acylation of 16 with diethyl oxalate (Formation of 18): A mixture of **16** (0.005 mol) and diethyl oxalate (1 ml) in absolute ethanol containing sodium metal (0.3 g) was refluxed for 10 h, then concentrated and cooled. The solid so obtained was washed with distilled water, dried and crystallised from ethanol to give **18** (40%), m.p. 95° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 300–3 100 (NH), 3 030 (aryl CH), 2 970–2 900 (aliph. CH), 1 780, 1 720 (C=O), 1 700–1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 1 480, 1 450 (def. CH), 1 250 (N–N) and 910, 830 cm⁻¹ (aryl...Ph).

Reaction of 18 with acetic anhydride (Isolation of compound 1): Compound **18** (0.005 mol) was refluxed in acetic anhydride (20 ml) for 2 h, then concentrated and cooled. The isolated solid was crystallised to give **1**.

4,6-Disubstituted-dihydro-1,2,4-triazine (19): An

equimolar mixture of **16** and *p*-bromophenylbromide in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and neutralised with dilute NaOH. The solid so obtained was crystallised (30%), m.p. 273° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 050 (aryl CH), 2 900 (aliph. CH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 1 480–1 450 (def. CH), 900, 830 (aryl...Ph) and 700–690 cm^{-1} (C–Br).

Fusion of 13 with benzoic acid hydrazide (Formation of 3,4-disubstituted-S-triazole 20): A mixture of **13** (0.01 mol) and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.01 mol) was fused under reflux for 4 h, then cooled and triturated with methanol to give **20** (20%), m.p. 327° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 050 (aryl CH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 1 560 (C=N) and 930, 830 cm^{-1} (aryl...Ph).

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Dr. Kamel A. El-Ghareeb, Microbiology Department, Faculty of Pharmacy, Al-Azhar

University, for the antimicrobial screening.

References

1. S. G. ABDEL-HAMIDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 000.
2. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1987, **30**, 490.
3. S. BAHADUR, N. SRIVASTAVA and M. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 684.
4. H. A. ZAHER, H. JAHINE, O. SHERIF and R. MOHAMMADY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, **18**, 316.
5. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, M. FAWZY, Y. GABAR, S. G. ABDEL-HAMIDE and A.T. SAID, *Indian J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1994, **3**, 281.
6. R. M. ABDEL-RAHMAN, Z. EL-GENDY, M. M. FAWZY and M. B. MAHMOUD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 628.
7. T. J. MACKIE and J. E. MAC CARTHENY, "Practical Medicinal Microbiology", 30th. ed., Churchill Livingstone, Edinburg, 1989, Vol. 2.